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Usability

Best Practices and General Rules

UI Design is “only” the tip of the iceberg

Fear the cognitive load like the plague!

Cognitive what?

- The cognitive load is based on the fact that short-term memory cannot store more than [7 +/- 2 items, only](#).
- If this limit is reached, then the user feels uncomfortable, and is less prone to explore your website.

Thus:

- In menus, do not exceed
 - 7 elements horizontally
 - 3 levels of depth vertically
- If more than 7 elements horizontally, those are hardly memorized by users
- If more than 3 levels of depth vertically, user won't be able to find anything

Ok, now, what should I do?

- Build a sitemap
- Validate the sitemap with users, by organizing card sorting sessions (30 sessions gives rise to a confidence of 90%).
- There are online tools for card sorting, you don't need to interact directly with users.
- There are also automatic tools to analyze the data.

Sitemap

- Contains
 - The categories of level 1, 2, and 3
 - The location of each page within the website
 - The list of elements (permanent, contextual)
- Enables to
 - Identify issues in the repartition of contents
 - Help the search engines
- Must be
 - Exhaustive
 - Understandable
 - intuitive

Find out more

Article by Nielsen Norman Group [“Minimize Cognitive Load to Maximize Usability”](#)

Don't make them think!

- People do not read, they scan
- Thus, use
 - Headings, sub-headings
 - Bullet-points
 - Short paragraphs
 - High contrast for call-to-action buttons
- Break up pages into clearly defined areas.
- Do not allow for too many choices
 - Use graphics to highlight the differences between the choices
 - Show the most popular ones.
- People usually don't read the doc, they directly struggle with the tool, which leads to lots of mistakes
 - Provide support
 - Use meaningful, and contextual error messages
 - Add tooltips, or a live chat
- Do not reinvent the wheel, but rather use the web conventions, which the users already know

Find out more

UX planet article [“Don't Make Me Think: 20 Wise Thoughts about Usability from Steve Krug.”](#)

Be empathic

- Use “Search”, “Print”, or “Send” in call-to-action buttons, rather than “OK”, or “Go”
- Do not put instructions in text fields, or find a way to keep the instructions visible after the user clicks on those fields
- Use button shaped call to actions rather than hyperlinks (or do it on purpose, for instance, add a “Cancel” hyperlink next to a call-to-action button)
- Get rid of visual noise
- Do not invent icons that users don't understand, and add labels to icons.
- Avoid:
 - Too small instructions
 - Poor contrast between elements and background
 - Jargon, unfamiliar words

Examples

1. Explicit action

2. Text fields instructions

3. Meaningful icon

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Color blindness

Defects of the cones lead to worsening of the colour vision. Depending on the seriousness of the defects, a human can mistake shades or lose ability to distinguish colours at all. For the majority of people, the disease is genetic. Colour blindness (or more specific colour vision deficiency –CVD) affects approximately every 1 in 12 men (8%) and 1 in 200 women (0.5%).

The most common types of colour blindness are due to the loss or limited function of red or green cone photopigments. This type of colour blindness is commonly referred to as red-green color blindness.

There are various type of color blindness, here the most known:

Name	Defect	Effect on the colours	Example		Frequency
Normal vision	-	-		-	
Red-Green colour blindness					
Deuteranaopia	No working green cone cells	Red appears brownish-yellow and green appears beige.			1% of males
Deuteranomaly	Green cone photopigment is abnormal	Yellow and green appear redder and it is difficult to tell violet from blue		most common — 6% of males, 0.4% of females	

Protanopia	No working red cone cells	Red appears as black. Certain shades of orange, yellow, and green all appear as yellow		1% of males	
Protanomaly	Red cone photopigment is abnormal	Red, orange, and yellow appear greener and colors are not as bright		1% of males, 0.01% of females	
Blue-Yellow colour blindness					
Tritanopia	No working blue cone cells	Blue appears green and yellow appears violet or light grey		Rare: less than 1% of males and females	
Tritanomaly	Functionally limited blue cone cells	Blue appears greener and it can be difficult to tell yellow and red from pink		Extremely rare: 0.01% of male and females	
Total colour blindness					
Achromatopsia (or rod monochromacy)	No cone cell with functional photopigments	Only see black white and grey		Extremely rare, recessive disorder	

Some tips and tricks to design a website for better colour accessibility:

Use both colours and symbols (icons or shapes). For example, certain types of colour blindness might make it difficult to see common red error messages: use both colours and symbols where users' attention is required

Alert messaging and required fields with text prefixes and icons

Use patterns and textures to show contrast. Use different textures, especially in graphs and charts, as opposed to multiple colours

Left, graphs viewed with normal vision; Right, graphs viewed with Protanopia.

Avoid bad colour combinations, such as:

- Green and Red
- Green and Brown
- Blue and Purple
- Green and Blue
- Light Green and Yellow
- Blue and Grey
- Green and Grey
- Green and Black

Left, color combinations viewed with normal vision; Right, same color combinations viewed with Protanopia.

Do not overlay text on background images, rather reduce the background opacity increasing the contrast

Add labels if colours cannot be changed, for instance in colour pickers or filters)

Left, color filter viewed with normal vision; Right color filter viewed with Protanopia

Add link recognition. Links should be easy to spot without relying on colour: always add an underline

Underlined links are easy to see by someone with achromatopsia.

Consider the contrast. This is particularly important when it comes to text placed on backgrounds. WCAG 2.1 guidelines state that colors should have a text-to-background contrast ratio of 4.5:1 for normal text and 3:1 for large text to meet basic AA requirements or 7:1 for normal text and 4.5:1 for large text to meet the stricter AAA requirements (always aim for strict).

Simple online tools allow checking those rules: <https://userway.org/contrast-checker>. Bear in mind that weight and emphasis (italic, bold etc) are also factors that affect the amount of contrast between a type and its background colour.

Add placeholders. Using a placeholder *without* a label is problematic because placeholder text usually lacks sufficient contrast

Left, bad example, not enough contrast; Right, good example, with placeholders

Use a colourblind friendly categorical palette for graphs and maps, such as the one used in this paper by Okabe & Ito (2002): <http://jfly.iam.u-tokyo.ac.jp/color/>

You can get this palette into a programming language using the RGB or CMYK values, or with the hex codes listed below. For example, you can create a colour palette in the programming language R, with the simple command:

```
cbPal <- c("#000000", "#E69F00", "#56B4E9", "#009E73", "#F0E442",
"#0072B2", "#D55E00", "#CC79A7")
```

Original	Simulation			Hue	for Photoshop, Illustrator, Freehand, etc.		for Word, Power Point, Canvas, etc.		
	Protan	Deutan	Tritan		C,M,Y,K (%)	R,G,B (0-255)	R,G,B (%)		
1		Black	-°	(0,0,0,100)	(0,0,0)	(0,0,0)			
2		Orange	41°	(0,50,100,0)	(230,159,0)	(90,60,0)			
3		Sky Blue	202°	(80,0,0,0)	(86,180,233)	(35,70,90)			
4		bluish Green	164°	(97,0,75,0)	(0,158,115)	(0,60,50)			
5		Yellow	56°	(10,5,90,0)	(240,228,66)	(95,90,25)			
6		Blue	202°	(100,50,0,0)	(0,114,178)	(0,45,70)			
7		Vermillion	27°	(0,80,100,0)	(213,94,0)	(80,40,0)			
8		reddish Purple	326°	(10,70,0,0)	(204,121,167)	(80,60,70)			

To go further:

Other excellent advice on creating colourblind friendly figures [in this blog post](#). Several applications allow simulating different types of colour blindness and visualizing the website as if. For Chrome, take a look at the [Colorblindly](#) extension.

In Coblis you can upload an image and take a look at what it'd look like through the eyes of people with different types of colour blindness. <https://www.color-blindness.com/coblis-color-blindness-simulator/>

Sources :

- <https://uxdesign.cc/color-blindness-in-user-interfaces-66c27331b858>
- <https://usabilla.com/blog/how-to-design-for-color-blindness/>
- <https://betterfigures.org/2015/06/23/picking-a-colour-scale-for-scientific-graphics/>
- <https://www.smashingmagazine.com/2016/06/improving-color-accessibility-for-color-blind-users/>
- <https://wave.webaim.org/> (a Web Accessibility Evaluation Tool)
- <https://www.w3.org/WAI/design-develop/> (Guidance for writing, designing, and developing for accessibility by W3C)
- <https://www.w3.org/WAI/tutorials/images/decision-tree/> (Accessibility of images by W3C)

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Data visualisation

Best Practices and General Rules

Do not use pies

Humans are bad at comparing angles, but very good at comparing lengths: therefore, you should favour bar charts over pies.

The only case where pies might make sense is when there 2 values to be compared, only.

3D is evil

3Ds vizes cause visual distortion and artefacts: therefore, you should stick to 2Ds.

Get rid of visual noise

To be well understood, and straight to the point, you should stick to "naked data vizes", that is:

- get rid of axis
- get rid of unnecessary zeros
- get rid of legends
- get rid of grids
- get rid of background/visual noise/icons/...
- do not use different colours if not absolutely necessary
- order the bars

Example:

Pick up the right visualisation for the right job

Allow only 1 message at a time.

In the example above, if the purpose is "Music Revenue by Format", do not split the values between children and adults, for instance, but rather stick to the simple bar chart representation.

Credits

This article is a summary of a workshop entitled "*Data Visualisation 101*", organised by Mira Nair (BioStrata) and Edmund Johnson (AbCam) at [UXLS 2019 conference](#).

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User surveys

“Surveys are useless until you know who it’s for and what you want to learn from it.”

What people say isn’t necessarily what they do.

User interviews that are based on task analysis usually focus on:

- Who they are (profile);
- What they do, when and where (context);
- Why they do it (needs, goals, tasks);
- How they do it (experience);
- What they like or dislike (frustrations).

How many people do you need to take a survey?

The number of respondents you need depends on your survey goals and how confident you want to be in your results. The more confident you want to be, the less of a margin of error you should accept.

In general, remember that, for an online/email survey, 20% of response rate is considered good; 30% is considered very good. In this infographic, you can find the average survey response rates for the most used survey methods based on the most recent data (source: <https://surveyanyplace.com/average-survey-response-rate/>)

So, to how many people do you need to send (or reach out with) your survey?

	Confidence level = 95%			Confidence level = 99%		
	Margin of error			Margin of error		
Population size	5%	2,5%	1%	5%	2,5%	1%
100	80	94	99	87	96	99
500	217	377	475	285	421	485
1.000	278	606	906	399	727	943
10.000	370	1.332	4.899	622	2.098	6.239
100.000	383	1.513	8.762	659	2.585	14.227
500.000	384	1.532	9.423	663	2.640	16.055
1.000.000	384	1.534	9.512	663	2.647	16.317

This table, indicates how many response you should have, depending on the population size, the margin of error and the confidence level. In red, the most used values. Note that, if the population size is 20'000, the sample will not impact the sample size anymore.

As a general rule, for a population of > 10'000, a good simple size at 95% of confidence level and 5% of margin of error, is ~380.

For a response rate of ~20%, one needs thus to reach out 1900 users.

A few definitions:

Margin of error: how much error surrounds a measure. It is a percentage that describes how much the opinions and behavior of the sample you survey is likely to deviate from the total population. It indicates a range of values above and below the actual results from a survey. The smaller the margin of error is, the closer you are to having the exact answer at a given confidence level. For example, a 5% of margin of error indicates that if you get a 60% “yes” response, for the total population (population size) this value is rather between 55% and 66%.

Confidence level: This number expresses how certain you are that the sample accurately reflects the attitudes of the total population. This tells you how sure you can be of the margin of error. It is expressed as a percentage and represents how often the true percentage of the population who would pick an answer lies within the margin of error. A confidence level at 95%, indicates that if the same survey were to be repeated 100 times under the same conditions, 95 times out of 100 the measure would lie somewhere within the margin of error. Researchers commonly set it at 90%, 95% or 99%.

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User Interviews

User interviews help us to gain a deeper understanding of people's behaviour and actions, so we could create a better product for them to use. Interviews are also one of the most commonly used methods in UX research, because it is a rather easy and cheap way to gain informations that we need.

First thing to know is what exactly is your target user. If you already made a stakeholder interview, you should know at this point what is the audience for the project, and based on those informations have your end-user profiles with specified metrics. What you need to do right now, is to reach out to people matching those criteria.

How to prepare for an interview

If you want to have a valuable outcome, you need to be prepared well. Write down a list of questions that will be your script and help you to guide an interview. Remember though that the interview should have a form of conversation, and the script is only a map for you, that helps you to keep the discussion on the right path.

At first, you should agree on what do you need to know from your users, what answers do you seek for.

Make sure that your questions are:

- non-leading—they don't suggest any answer or any general approach to the topic
- open-ended—it will help you to avoid non-productive interviews, that won't give you too many valuable insights
- specific and clear—speak the language that is understandable for your your respondent, keep your questions short and ask only one question at the time.

To be prepared for an interview you will also have to plan how to gather the data you will get through the session.

The most comfortable way to do it is to record the interview—it enables you to be more concentrated on your respondent, don't miss anything important, but also to analyse a non-verbal way of answering questions—like facial expressions, body language, tone of voice—that will help you to better understand your respondent.

Remember to always ask about permission to record, explain the aim of it and provide information on who will have an access to those recordings.

If you won't decide to record an interview, you can do the note taking—by yourself or with a help of another person.

How to conduct an interview

Intro

Start your interview with a short intro, while you will introduce yourself and explain the reason for your research. Try to break the ice, create an atmosphere of trust and make your respondent feel comfortable—warm up questions that you have prepared before will help you with that.

Before getting to the questions it is important to explain to respondent that there are no right or bad answers to your question, assure him that what you really need is his honest feedback.

An Interview

During the interview remember that you're the one to steer it to right direction. So if your respondent tend to talk a lot (which is stil a good thing) remember about the script and make sure that you're not getting too far from the main topic.

On the other hand, your respondent may be not that talkative, and give you very short answers. In that case you should ask some additional questions, prompt for more details.

From time to time make some follow ups—it will not only help you to make sure you got the answers right, but also will show your respondent that you're listening carefully and it will give your interview more conversational form.

Wrap up

At the end of the interview it's always good to ask if there is something more that your respondent would like to add or to ask you about—it is a good way to give a sense of closure but also can give you some additional insights. Always thank your respondent for his time and let him know that gathered informations are valuable and helpful.

(source: <https://uxplanet.org>)

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Personas

Personas are fictional characters which are stand-ins for user types that might use your product or service in a similar way, but they are not based solely on demographic survey data.

Numerous research data for product design are quite difficult to handle, especially when we need to pay attention to the data throughout the entire process. Therefore, Persona will be a relatively more realistic and concrete object, although not a real person, it is the most typical image of many real Personas. And it can remind us of the users' needs and help us make a better user experience model because of which real users will feel more comfortable while using product. This is why it can facilitate the development.

Remember that every good persona is based on **solid data**. If you didn't have anything to start with, perform **user interviews** or **user surveys** first: proper personas are created based upon direct **user research** and represent the users' needs, experiences, behaviors, and goals. Gathered data tends to overlap, it's where you should look for patterns. You can divide them into persona for each overlap.

Persona is simply a representation of your most common target audience. It'll help you standardise needs and get solutions faster. You can think of it as a folder with your similar users.

How to create a persona?

Step 1. Take a closer look to your data.

The first step is to take a closer look to your data gathered in Discovery Phase, especially User Interview. Tag your most important insights, mainly problems. We have added the brainstorming tool to the Supplementary Data to help you focus.

Step 2. Identify patterns

Once you gather some data to analyse, it's time to identify patterns. It's time to take a closer look at tagged data to see if overlap emerge naturally. In this point you should see that different groups of people have novel approach to the subject.

Step 3. Create persona

In general, a persona should have those four main elements:

1. **Photo & Name:** they help you impersonate your user, you will call him/her by name and think at him/her as a "real" person
2. **Description and Behaviour:** who is s/he? how old is s/he? what is her/his background? what does s/he like? how does s/he behave?
3. **Needs and Goals:** what is s/he looking for? why does s/he needs the tool?
4. **Frustrations:** why can't s/he use existing tool? what is missing? what doesn't s/he like?

You can add as many detail as you wish, however **those 4 should never be missing**. In the Supplementary Data, we have created a template for you to create the right persona.

Step 4. Think with your persona

Now, you should become a friend with your persona: once you're talking about new feature, think what Simon —your main Persona would think about it and how it's inline with his motivations.

We have added for you 2 personas to the Supplementary Data to see some examples.

Sources :

- <https://uxls.org/>
- <https://uxplanet.org>

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User journey

'How do people actually use our product?' is a fundamental question that every product creator must answer. In order to answer this question, product designers need to understand the essence of the whole experience from the user's perspective. User journey mapping is an excellent exercise that can shed light on that.

User journey map is a visualization of an individual's relationships with a product/brand over time and across different channels.

User journey map comes AFTER you created the persona and it's customized for him/her and his/her experience with the tool.

In the Supplementary Data, we have created for you a simplified user journey template to help you get through the experience.

To see some examples, have a look at the user journeys of Guillaume and Bibiana in the Supplementary Data.

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Google Analytics

Step-by-step

Introduction

Google analytics is used to track the website activity of the users such as session duration, pages per session, bounce rate etc. along with the information on the source of the traffic. Google Analytics analysis can identify poorly performing pages, where visitors came from, how long they stayed on the website and their geographical position.

Select a period of time of one year, view per week

- **Audience overview** (if possible, compare to the previous year)
 - **NB:** *Bounce rate <70% is considered good*
- Geographical distribution: Audience- Overview – click on Country
- Browser usage: Audience- Overview – click on Browser
- OS usage: Audience- Overview – click on Operating System
- Acquisition overview
 - Organic Search: *users reach the website without clicking a link on another site (referral traffic) or clicking an ad (paid traffic) - e.g. Google Search.*
 -
 - Check for keywords
 - Direct: *users reach the website by typing the correct URL.*
 - Referral: *traffic that occurs when a user finds the website through a site other than a major search engine.*
 - Check for source
- **Behavior overview**
 - Site Content All Pages report (Behaviour - Site Content - All Pages)
 - Behaviour – Site Content – Landing Pages (*/ is homepage in general*)
 - *Check Bounce Rate, Pages/Sessions (which is the number of web pages each visitor views on average after landing on the webpage. Compare this metric with other landing pages to determine if a particular page is performing better or worse than average.), Avg. Session Duration*
 - *Check also Traffic Source as 2ndary dimension, Sources and Referral Path, to know where the visitor was before entering the website*
- Behaviour – Site Content – Exit Pages
- Device report (Audience - Mobile - Overview)?
- Behaviour Flow report (Behaviour - Behaviour Flow)?
- Social:
 - Acquisition-Social-Network Referrals
 - Acquisition-Social-Landing Pages
- If used: Google Search Console
- If the resource tracks the EVENTS: Events Overview report (Behaviour - Events – Overview)
- If the resource tracks the search terms: (Behaviour - Site Search - Overview)?

Bots and spiders

Google Analytics **does not filter out bots by default**, you have to set it explicitly in your settings (*Admin > View Settings > Bot filtering > Exclude all hits from known bots and spiders*). Please note that the list of bots and spiders which Google Analytics considers are the most common ones. If you want to filter out your own IPs, or domain names, etc., you will have to use the custom filters (*Admin > Filters*).

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SEO

Search Engine Optimisation

(Source: [99techpost](#))

Introduction

96% of Europeans use Google (this rate drops to 75% worldwide).

In the result page, **40-60%** of people click on the first non-commercial link, this rate drops to **10%** for the second link!

Being well indexed is thus crucial for the visibility of your resource, or service!

Each website is assigned a score by Google. Although the scoring algorithm not fully transparent, and continuously evolving, Google relies on the following criteria:

- quality of the code (use the [W3C validator](#))
- site in https
- responsive design
- multi-language site
- short domain name
- good ratio between text and tags (15% of tags, max)
- good eTrust (use the [WOT plugin](#) to check the e-reputation of your website)
- well-established site

What should you do to boost your resource's score?

- use logos to go back to the home page
- add a search field
- optimised 404 pages
- breadcrumbs
- speed: The indexing rate is linked to the page response time (Google allow a certain amount of time to index an entire website)
 - Minimised files
 - No slideshow, Googlemap, etc... on the home page
- images + links: add alt properties
- header tags: Do not skip tags, use h1, h2, h3, ... in this order
- use tags for important text
- check that the links to external website are not broken

With well-chosen semantic keywords, Google will easily recognize the meaning of page content. First define your main keyword, and then 10-15 secondary keywords (for this, you can use [Google Trends](#)), and use them:

- in the URL (domain name + sub-domains)
- in the page title
- in a top-menu
- in the <h1> tag, and then in the <h2> tags (in this order)
- in the text

And what about images?

In 2018, [over 20% of all U.S. web searches happened on Google Images](#). Plus, with advancements in **voice search technology**, media is a growing importance.

Here are examples of image optimization tips:

- Format:
 - PNG: Produces better quality images, but comes with a larger file size.
 - JPEG: Lower image quality.
- Compress the images (with Photoshop or [TinyPNG](#), for instance). To check in what extend your images are affecting your page speed, use Google's [PageSpeed Insights](#) tool.
- Create unique images, avoid generic stock photos.
- Beware of copyright!
- Customized image file names: Creating descriptive, keyword-rich file names is absolutely crucial (databases-gene-expression.png over IMG_722019.png).
- SEO-friendly Alt text (use 'overview databases gene expression' over 'database').
- Image file structure: The file path and file name is an actual ranking factor! Use sub-folders such as /media/databases over the generic /media/
- Page title & description: Google uses the page title and description as part of its image search algorithm.
- Image dimensions: It's a best practice to define the width and height of your images. It provides a better user experience.

- Make your images mobile-friendly
- Add images to your sitemap (for crawlability)

Article by Search Engine Journal “[12 Important Image SEO Tips You Need To Know](#)”

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Supplementary Data

Brainstorming:

What are the needs that the tool wants to meet?

How does it meet the needs?

How does it compares to the competitors, if existing? Why is it better?

Discovering the user community: who are the users?

Let's meet Simon. Simon is...

Description & Behaviour

(who is he? what is his background?
what does he like?
how does he behave?)

Needs & Goals

(what is he looking for?
why does he needs the tool?)

Frustrations

(why can't he use existing tool?
what is missing?
what doesn't he like?)

Bibiana

AGE: 35

LOCATION: Bogota (Colombia)

POSITION: Post-doc (Biochemistry)

EMPLOYER: University of Bogota

BACKGROUND: PhD (Biochemistry),
New-York University, 2013

SKILLS:

Biochemistry

Pharmacy

Technology

Bibiana is a young Colombian scientist, who was trained as Biochemist. After 10 years in New-York (USA), she is now back in Bogota, in a multidisciplinary Colombian team of researchers composed of Botanists, Ethnologists, Geographers, Chemists, and Pharmacists. The mission of the team is to explore the Amazonian primary forest, in order to collect unknown plants samples, from which molecules of potential pharmaceutical interest are extracted. She receives the molecule formulas from her Chemists colleagues, and she wants to compare them with existing pharmaceutical compounds in the drug databases. She wants to explore the results, and depending on the potential pharmaceutical interest, she wants to rate the molecules for further analysis at the lab.

BIBIANA'S GOALS

- I want a reliable and **accurate tool** to see whether the molecule I have could be of potential interest
- The team needs my input to decide whether or not we should invest time (and money) to study a given molecule
- I need a tool which is **fast, and easy to use**, because I don't have time to try to understand technology
- I am very excited about this mission, and I hope we will manage to find drugs from the plants

BIBIANA'S CONCERNS

- In general, I am **reluctant to use automatic tools** in my research, I hope I will manage to find one I trust
- I have **a lot of pressure** on my shoulders, because the success of this project depends of the choices I will make about the molecules

BIBIANA'S CHARACTER

- Curious
- Passionate about science, and pre-colombian history
- Impatient

Guillaume, 37

Senior researcher

Description

Senior researcher, chemical and structural biologist

University of Madras, Chennai, India

PhD in Structural Biology
MSc in Bioinformatics
BSc in Chemistry

Background

Guillaume is a member of the group of System Biology at the University of Madras, India. He started 4 years ago, after a Ph.D. in UK. His research now is in collaboration with a local non-profit company and focuses on the drug design of a potential drug equivalent to an existing expensive one to treat pneumonia. He generally starts with a broad hypothesis that gets narrowed down. His project has limited funding, therefore he cannot use commercial tools.

Needs and goals

- > “I need to know if a model can work through a quick overview of generic properties of the molecules I am testing.”
- > “I need a tool that gives results with high scientific accuracy.”
- > “I need a flexibility of a free platform that can do single/multiple analysis and rerun the results.”
- > “I need to download the data into various formats for further analysis and visual graphs for presentations and papers.”

Frustrations

- > “I cannot afford a commercial tool.”
- > “The available free tools have a low scientific quality.”
- > “The existing tools are not interoperable and I lose a lot of time in comparing the results”.
- > “When I show the results to the stakeholders, I have to show them something that is easy-to-read and well summarized, otherwise they do not understand.”

User Journey: How does the user interact with the system? What is he doing/thinking? How does he feel?

	Start What does the user want to know? Why is he there?	Use How does the user start?	Interpret What does he do with the results? Do the results answer his question?
Actions			
Thinking			
Feelings 			
Opportunities			

Bibiana - User Journey

— STAGES

Use Google, forums, Pubmed

Open the website

Read the reference paper

Enter the molecule

Select the lib/ method

Run the job

Explore the results

Export/score the results

— QUESTIONS/CONCERNS

Where can I find the tool I need?

Is there a tool at all?

Does the website correspond to what I need?

Is it easy to use?

Is it going to work quickly?

I have to validate the website info with a scientific paper.

All right, the paper convinced me

How can I enter my data?

Which order of the steps?

What is the format?

Which method should is the most suitable for my needs?

Which criteria should I use to choose one?

Did I take the right one?

How much time will it take?

Will the result be significant/ accurate?

Which output format will I get?

What is the score?

How can I compare 2 results?

I cannot download my query

I cannot download one result at a time

— EMOTIONS

— OPPORTUNITIES

Improve SEO

Improve Teaching

Improve outreach

Improve social media policy

Add an onboarding tutorial

Make the example more visible

Add tooltips/ help

Make the ordering of the steps more logical

Tooltips/help for the libs/ method

Pre-select lib/ method

Make the ordering of the steps more logical

Add an estimated time

Add a STOP button

Add a tooltip to the score

Add score benchmarking document

Allow for comparison of 2 molecules

Add a download menu to each result panel

Guillaume: Senior researcher

